

INNOVATIVE METHODOLOGY BY USING DIC TO IDENTIFY INTRALAMINAR DAMAGE IN CFRP WITHIN AN INDUSTRIAL CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

Within the context of virtual structural testing, one way of modeling degradation phenomena in composites is via continuum damage mechanics. It is important to validate these models with experimental observations and quantifications of microcracks in terms of density and opening. In order to detect and quantify transverse cracking in layered composites, global Digital Image Correlation (DIC) is applied to a series of optical images of a coupon side during tensile tests. Two different methodologies are developed and compared in order to assess the presence of microcracks. Both of them are based on the measurements of displacement profiles in 90° plies. The first method is based on the analysis of axial strain fields. The second method exploits an a priori expectation of the shape of the displacement field in the vicinity of transverse cracks based on a shear lag model. Both methods provide identical results for thick 90° plies, but the second one appears more sensitive than the former for thin plies.

1 Introduction

Virtual structural testing is one of the major challenges facing aeronautical industries in order to reduce product development costs by relying on a more limited number of physical tests. Airbus Group has chosen to use physically-based models for the detailed expertise and analysis of its structures made of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP). This choice is justified by the predictive capacity of these approaches to describe the driving forces of all the degradation mechanisms up to failure (i.e. matrix cracking, interface delamination, fiber breakage).

This work deals with the characterization of transverse cracking through tensile tests on $[0^\circ/90^\circ]^s$ laminates. Standard methods consist of optical monitoring by microscopy, acoustic emission and X-ray radiography. For optical monitoring, the test has to be interrupted many times to allow for a manual crack count on the specimen side. Sometimes, pictures are recorded on the fly during the test and subsequently analyzed. This method is highly operator-dependent. The analyses via acoustic emission are mostly qualitative. Even though the damage threshold may be determined, an accurate crack counting is very difficult to perform. Last, X-ray radiography requires tests to be interrupted to enable an inspection. It produces a clear visualization of each crack, easy to count but difficult to implement on a routine basis.

Two alternative approaches are followed herein. They consist of post-processing displacement fields measured via Digital Image Correlation (DIC). The first one is an indirect approach in which the presence of microcracks is described by an additional strain contribution. The second one consists of analyzing the displacement field. For the first approach, the challenge is to experimentally count intralaminar cracks. For the second approach, the scale of measurement may prevent the displacement details from being detectable.

2 Technical Background

The description and prediction of damage states in layered composites are challenging because they occur at very small scales and they are distributed within the whole material. The main assumption is to consider damage as combination of several and successive degradation mechanisms. The most important ones are, in order of appearance, interfacial fiber/matrix debonding, transverse microcracking across the thickness of elementary plies, interface delamination, and fiber breakage. Airbus Group Innovations has chosen to use a Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) framework to model all these mechanisms. The microscopic validation of LMT-Cachan mesomodel [1,2] is aimed for. The model is defined by means of two mesoconstituents, namely, layers and inter-ply interfaces. Each constituent is considered as continuous and independent of the full laminate. The model describes the total damage process by accounting for intralaminar and interlaminar degradations. A uniform damage state is assumed through the thickness of the elementary ply, which defines the mesoscopic scale.

By resorting to Continuum Thermodynamics [3], the formulation of damage laws consists of identifying the relationship of each damage variable d_{ij} with its associated thermodynamic force Y_{ij} . The latter corresponds to the energy release rate density

$$Y_{ij} = \frac{\partial \langle E_d \rangle}{\partial d_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the average of the elastic energy density E_d over the thickness of the considered ply, and $i,j=1,2$ the two in-plane directions. In the following, the only studied degradation mechanism is transverse cracking, which usually follows diffuse fiber/matrix debonding and precedes delamination.

It is worth noting that this model is built at the mesoscale, while most of the degradations initiate at the microscale. There is therefore a need for bridging these two scales [4]. The associated model is based on a hybrid approach linking CDM and fracture mechanics to account for the discreteness of this mechanism. To identify such damage experimental techniques able to quantify these discrete events are desirable.

3 Experimental Protocol

The specimen geometry used for all tests is shown in figure 1. The laminates are manufactured from carbon/epoxy unidirectional prepregs. The nominal ply thickness is 0.13 mm. Several $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ lay-ups are considered to study transverse cracking. The main interest of these lay-ups is to initiate

brittle cracks in pure mode I and in the whole coupon width of 90° layers. Three thicknesses of 90° plies are investigated:

- Lay-up 1: $[0_6, 90_4, 0_6]$
- Lay-up 2: $[0_5, 90_6, 0_5]$
- Lay-up 3: $[0_4, 90_8, 0_4]$

Figure 1: Sample dimensions

Prior to the test, the specimens are quality controlled by ultra sound scans to confirm that they are delamination-free. The coupon sides are checked by microscopic inspection to exclude any sample with transverse crack due to machining. One side is painted with an airbrush to create a black & white random pattern (figure 2). The specimen is mounted in a servohydraulic tension/compression testing machine. Monotonic and quasi static loading is applied on each specimen until failure. A CCD camera of definition 2320×1728 pixels associated with a $\times 0.5$ telecentric lens is placed in front of the painted side. The observed window is 33-mm long. Prior to loading, a first set of pictures is acquired. It allows for an evaluation of displacement and strain resolutions. Approximately 500 pictures are recorded per test at a rate of 0.5 frame per second.

Figure 2: Schematic view of the optical setup and example of a picture of the prepared surface

Q4-DIC [5,6], which is a global DIC algorithm, is used to measure 2D surface displacement fields. It allows for the measurement of continuous displacement fields associated with finite-element discretizations. Bilinear shape functions associated with 4-noded quadrilateral elements are chosen. The physical size of one pixel is equal to 0.015 mm. For this study, 16-pixels elements are chosen. It corresponds to a good compromise between the standard displacement resolution and the spatial resolution (16 pixels \leftrightarrow 0.24 mm). The standard resolution is obtained by registering the 10 pictures acquired with no applied load. The standard displacement resolution corresponds to the standard deviation of the measured fields (here equal to 0.016 pixel). Similarly, the standard strain resolution is found to be of the order of 10^{-3} .

From the measured displacement fields, transverse cracks are detected and characterized. Figure 3 shows longitudinal displacement and strain fields measured with the commercial code Correli STC[®] [6]. Although no specific analysis is performed, these fields highlight the existing transverse cracks thanks to high apparent strains that are concentrated in the 90° plies.

Figure 3: Longitudinal displacement and strain fields of $[0_4,90_8,0_4]$ lay-up

4 Detection and Quantification Methods

4.1 Analysis of Strain Fields

The first method of crack quantification is based on the analysis of the longitudinal strain fields. One essential feature of DIC, as for any measurement tool, is to provide a displacement measurement that is endowed with an uncertainty σ_u that depends on the chosen spatial resolution. The more spatially resolved the displacement field, the higher the displacement uncertainty. At the scale of one single Q4 element, the standard strain uncertainty is such that $\sigma_\varepsilon \propto \sigma_u / \ell$ [7].

A crack leads to a displacement jump Δu . For an element containing a crack, the estimate of the mean element strain results in a strain increment $\Delta \varepsilon = \Delta u / \ell$. For a given displacement jump, for small element sizes the apparent strain is dominated by the uncertainty, and hence it cannot be measured. For large element sizes, the uncertainties decrease more rapidly than the sought signal, and hence cracks can be detected reliably provided the distance between them is large enough as compared to the element size. The minimum element size will depend on the detectable amplitude of the displacement jump.

From the measured displacement fields, the Q4-DIC code calculates the mean strain per element. The elements belonging to 90° plies are selected. The fields are averaged in the transverse direction and then displayed as a function of the longitudinal abscissa per recorded picture. Each local

maximum is considered as a signature of a transverse crack. Based on the evaluation of the standard strain resolution σ_{ϵ} , a threshold is defined (i.e., $20 \times \sigma_{\epsilon}$). Then, an algorithm detects, counts, and localizes each transverse crack (see figure 4).

Figure 4: Detection steps of cracks in measured strain field

4.2 Analysis of Displacement Fields

The presence of a crack leads to a change in the displacement field (figure 5). By using a shear lag model [8,9], the displacement modification induced by the presence of a crack consists of two discontinuous parabolas (figure 6). The amplitude of the discontinuity corresponds to the crack opening displacement (COD) and $2Ldt$ the size of the obscuration zone.

Figure 5: Typical displacement profile when numerous cracks are present. The red ellipse shows one of the cracks

For an initial obscuration length Ldt (e.g. equal to the element size ℓ), the cross-correlation product between the adjusted displacement field (figure 5) and the reference displacement field (figure 6) is computed. The former is determined by subtracting to the measured displacement the affine contribution. In the latter a unit displacement jump is assumed. If the correlation product is larger than a threshold that depends on the standard displacement resolution, a crack is detected. By varying the obscuration length, the crack opening displacement is the value of the maximum level of the correlation product, and the location is where the maximum is reached. Once this zone is determined, it is assumed that no new crack will initiate and it is excluded from subsequent analyses.

Figure 6: Key features associated with a displacement field around a crack according to shear-lag hypotheses

5 Results

Figure 7 shows for each analyzed test with lay-up 1 the change of the crack density with the macroscopic mean strain. A symbol corresponds to the strain field analysis of a recorded picture. These curves have three important features, namely, the strain level for the first crack inception, the rate of growth and the crack density at saturation.

Figure 7: Crack density evaluated from the strain field analysis for lay-up 1

Figure 8 shows the results of both methods for all the analyzed tests. The first striking feature is that in general both methods provide a rather consistent measurement of the crack density, including the strain at initiation and the crack density at saturation. This holds for all samples of the lay-up with the largest stack of 90° plies (lay-up 3) but also that with the smallest number considered herein (lay-up 1). Unexpectedly, the intermediate case (lay-up 2) shows some discrepancies. The result shown here corresponds to an element size of $\ell = 16$ pixels, and hence a zone influenced by the crack to amount to at the least twice that size (i.e., 32 pixels).

Figure 8: Comparison of crack density evaluations by both methods for all the analyzed cases

When the obscuration length Ldt is chosen to be 24 pixels, two datasets (r3n5 and r3n7) determined with the shear lag analysis are brought in coincidence with the data extracted from the strain criterion as shown in Figure 9. In contrast, when a smaller length ($Ldt = 8$ pixels) is chosen, the data becomes

very steep and saturates very early on at a value that is much too high in terms of density when compared to a microscopic analysis. Similar observations can be made for the strain criterion when a chosen element is too small.

Figure 9: Comparison of crack density evaluations by both methods for lay-up no.2 with $Ldt = 24$ pixels

In conclusion, both procedures can be tuned to provide rather consistent results (at the exception of one case r3n3 of lay-up 2). However, they do require fulfilling specific conditions for their applicability. In particular the strain method requires at least two or three elements between two cracks to be able to distinguish them, and it is observed that the studied cases are very close to this limit. Smaller elements show a higher uncertainty and hence the detection threshold has to be increased to be safe from noise, and hence some microcracks may be missed or the analysis may be corrupted by noise. The shear lag model is much closer to the expected behavior and hence should be expected to be more reliable. However, the above illustrated difficulty is the need to have a faithful evaluation of the obscuration length.

Let us come back to the requirement of the measurement using the second protocol. It is observed that the detection of cracks can be seen as a deconvolution of the displacement field by a specific crack displacement signature. Hence, in addition to the discontinuity, which is the signature of the crack itself, the displacement field contains an extended neighborhood where obscuration occurs. This offers much more information and hence it has the potential of being much more precise than the first method, which only uses the crack discontinuity. Because the signature is spread over several elements, it becomes theoretically possible to detect a crack below the strain uncertainty that would be the limit of the first method. The cooperative contribution of the surrounding is all the more beneficial as the influence of cracks is large. It is also to be stressed that the actual shape of the crack signature may not be extremely accurate as the obscuration length for instance is expected not to be a material property but rather a function of the prescribed macroscopic strain as delamination will propagate from the crack position along the ply interfaces. Yet, the cross-correlation technique used herein is tolerant to such modulations provided the discrepancy is not too large. Therefore, the second method is expected to be the most sensitive provided the crack pattern is accurately depicted. This observation raises as a perspective the possibility to “learn” the pattern from a first detection. Averaging the local displacement perturbation due to cracks that have been detected may provide an empirical determination of this influence function, devoid of any specific modelling.

As a longer term perspective, one may today envision a two dimensional approach for such a crack detection approach. However, it has to allow for a very fine spatial resolution (i.e. fine mesh to describe the kinematics) and yet a rather long regularization length in order to benefit from the large scale influence of the crack opening. These two requirements seem conflicting. Mechanical regularization strategies applied to fine meshes allow these two organic length scales to be separated.

The short scale is chosen for the mesh, and the large one for mechanical regularization [10]. If an elastic behavior is used for the regularization then the role of the mesh disappears and the crack discontinuity is smeared over a large region and has a small influence. The incorporation of “damage” into the regularization kernel allows the regularization length scale to be reduced precisely where the strain level is the largest. This approach seems a promising route to follow, and some examples have shown its good potential [11]. However, a more systematic study of a robust algorithm to drive this progressive damage is needed to turn a research tool into a more reliable approach. These developments will be reported in a forthcoming study.

6 Conclusion and Perspectives

The reported results show that photomechanics, and particularly DIC, provides a simple and friendly access to minute displacement features occurring at small scales that capture the physical origin of composite damage. This result is key to validate continuum damage mechanics models through upscaling, and therefore to assess the reliability and trustworthiness of large scale simulations of composite structures.

However, it is to be underlined that for industrial applications, the goal is not to be able to achieve such a characterization once in very well mastered conditions, but rather to turn this approach into a very robust tool for non experts and yet provide reliable and reproducible results. Such a goal can be reached:

- if the image definition is high enough as compared to the ply thickness that is considered and then the two methods studied herein are equivalent,
- and when the latter definition becomes limiting, the second method, which is more faithful to the actual mechanical behavior, provides a more sound and robust result.

However, in all cases, it is important to define the appropriate conditions and scale for which the results are trustworthy as the quest for smaller and smaller microcracks can be an endless story.

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